

Alleviation of metal stress using an extremotolerant PGPR isolated from date palm rhizosphere in Tunisia.

Sawsen Hnichir, Mayssa Belhassan, Hamida Barhoumi, Amine Elleuch and Bassem Khemakhem.

¹ Laboratory of Plant Biotechnology Applied to the Improvement of Cultures, Faculty of Sciences of Sfax, University of Sfax, B.P. 1171, 3000, 3029 Sfax, Tunisia

The Sainsbury Laboratory, University of East Anglia, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, United Kingdom.

Abstract:

In this work, the analysis of the whole genome sequence (WGS) of *Bacillus filamentosus* IG3, an extremotolerant plant growth promoting bacterium isolated from the date palm rhizosphere, is presented. The complete genome sequence of this strain will provide valuable insights into the roles of key genes related to its extreme-tolerance ability, PGPR traits as well as its mechanisms of action to mitigate heavy metal stress.

Introduction:

The rhizosphere is a highly dynamic niche in which microorganisms and plants develop complex biochemical and physical contacts (Bhattacharyya et al., 2017; Niazi et al., 2014). Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) are a group of bacteria found in plants rhizosphere and can facilitate and enhance plant development in both normal and stressed environments (Liu et al., 2022). PGPR enhances plant growth through several mechanisms, including increasing nutrient uptake (phosphorus and potassium), nitrogen fixation, ACC deaminase activity, phytohormones and siderophores production (Rikame et al., 2022; Jirakkakul et al., 2023). In addition, certain rhizobacteria also have more specific PGP traits, such as salinity tolerance, heavy metal alleviation activity, and biocontrol activity against phytopathogens and insects (Liu et al., 2016).

Bacillus is one of the typical PGPR genus that can be applied as bio-inoculants and biocontrol agents to stimulate plant growth by enhancing plant biomass, enhancing seedling emergence, and limiting disease impact (Yin et al., 2022; Du et al., 2019). They are endospore forming Gram positive bacteria and ubiquitous in different natural environments. Members of the

genus *Bacillus*, such as *B. pumilus*, *B. subtilis*, *B. licheniformis*, *B. atrophaeus*, *B. vallismortis*, *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. mojavensis*, *B. paralicheniformis*, *B. sonorensis* and *B. tequilensis*, have been used as PGPR strains (Narayanasamy et al., 2023).

Recently, the whole genome sequencing (WGS) and functional analysis of PGPR genomes have uncovered the molecular mechanisms of their beneficial activity which led to the identification of several genes implicated in the PGPR-plant interaction (Guerrieri et al., 2021). In this work, the WGS of *B. filamentousus* IG3 strain offer insight into the molecular basis underlying its mechanisms of action to enhance plant growth under normal and stressful conditions (heavy metals and salinity).

Material and methods:

Bacteria isolation:

Bacillus filamentousus IG3, isolated from rhizospheric soil date palm trees were used in this work. For IG3 bacterium isolation, serial dilution technique was adopted. A 0.1ml of serially diluted aliquot was spread on Luria Bertani agar medium pH 9 and incubated at a range of temperatures between 45 and 60 °C for 48 h. After incubation, morphologically distinct colonies were purified, and stored in glycerol stocks.

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA:

Bacterium DNA extraction, genome sequencing and assembly were done according to the guidelines provided by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK, <https://microbesng.com>). The total DNA quantification and library preparation were conducted on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland) and were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) with a 250 pb paired-end strategy. Reads were further trimmed Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. Obtained reads fragments were further assembled by SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012). The genome was annotated using Prokka version 1.11 (Seemann., 2014).

Results:

Genomic Features:

The strain IG3 genome was assembled into 23 contigs indicative of 5055177 base pairs with an average G+C content of 36,42%, an *N50* of 3371643 bp, an *L50* value of 1 and the largest contig was 3371643bp. In total 5,123 genes encoding 4,972 protein coding sequences (CDSs), 9 ribosomal RNA (rRNA) genes and 75 genes of transfer RNA (tRNA) were found in IG3 genome (Table1). The ANI (Average Nucleotide Identity) and the taxonomic nomenclature revealed that IG3 strain exhibited an identity 88.96 % with *B. filamentousus* species. The *Bacillus filamentousus* whole genome sequence assembly has been deposited at GenBank (accession no. JAVSIX000000000).

Table1: Summary statistics for *Bacillus filamentousus* IG3 genome assembled from Illumina reads.

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus filamentousus</i>
Genome size (bp)	5063500
Contigs (>= 1000 bp)	23
Largest contig	3371643
GC (%)	36,42
N50	3371643
L50	1
Genes	5,123
rRNA	9
tRNAs	75
Bio-sample	SAMN37346815
GenBank accession (reads)	SRR26109195
GenBank accession (Assembly)	JAVSIX000000000

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